

Studies on Coagulation and Electrical Properties of Copper Ferrocyanide, Nickel Ferricyanide, and Ceric Oxide Hydrosols

Samir Kumar Sengupta and Nityananda Kundu

ζ -Potentials, corrected for surface conductance effect, and the limiting concentrations of the equicoagulating counter ions, beyond which surface conductance does not play any part, have been calculated for copper ferrocyanide, nickel ferricyanide, and ceric oxide hydrosols. The coagulation has been explained in terms of the equation:

$$\zeta_s = A + B \log \Sigma c_i,$$

where Σc_i represents the total equicoagulating concentration of the added counter ions at which the ζ -potential (ζ_s) is measured, and A and B are constants.

Copper ferrocyanide, nickel ferricyanide, and ceric oxide sols were prepared in order to study their coagulation and to measure their ζ -potentials.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper ferrocyanide and nickel ferricyanide sols were prepared by peptising thoroughly washed precipitates of copper ferrocyanide and nickel ferricyanide, obtained by addition of $N/10$ - CuSO_4 solution to $N/10$ - $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution and $N/10$ - NiSO_4 solution to $N/10$ - $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution, respectively. After dialysis and aging for 15 days, the negatively charged sols were found to possess sp. conductance of 2.48×10^{-4} and 2.99×10^{-4} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 25°. The ceric oxide sol was prepared by electrolysing a hydrolysed solution (0.5%) of ceric ammonium nitrate. After aging the sol was found to possess a sp. conductance of 1.04×10^{-4} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 25°.

Equicoagulating concentrations in the rapid zone and in the slow zone (for CeO_2 sol only) were found and the ζ -potentials were measured at different equicoagulating concentrations of the added counter ions by electro-osmotic and/or microcataphoretic experiments, as described in a previous communication¹.

DISCUSSION

From the results represented in Fig. 1 and 2, it is evident that the measured ζ -potential (ζ_s) decreases with decreasing equicoagulating concentrations of the counter ions and hence with decreasing specific conductance (S) of the supernatant solutions,

1. Kundu and Moulk, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 705.

2. Kundu, this *issue*, p. 295.

Since the conditions of the experiments were so adjusted that the surface-conductance effect would only be prominent (the concentrations of the counter ions being considerably high, the relaxation effect will play no part). application of Ghosh's equations (1) and (2). (vide reference 2) would lead to the evaluation of ζ -potential corrected for surface-conductance effect (ζ_a).

FIG. 1

Copper ferrocyanide sol.	Nickel ferricyanide sol.	Ceric oxide sol.
Electro-osmosis I.	Electro-osmosis II.	Electro-osmosis IV and microcataphoresis V.
1,2: $C_6H_5NH_2HCl + BaCl_2$.	1,2: $KCl + BaCl_2$.	1: KBr .
3: $KCl + MgCl_2$.	3: $KCl + MgCl_2$.	2,3: $KBr + Na-succinate$.
4: $MgCl_2$.	4: $MgCl_2$.	4: $KBr + K_3Fe(CN)_6$.
5: $BaCl_2$.	5: $BaCl_2$.	5: $K_3Fe(CN)_6$.
6: $La(NO_3)_3$.	6: $KCl + La(NO_3)_3$.	
	7: $BaCl_2 + La(NO_3)_3$.	
	8: $La(NO_3)_3$.	
	8: $La(NO_3)_3$.	

The validity of the equation:

$$\zeta_a = A + B \log \Sigma c_1$$

[where Σc_1 represents the total equicoagulating concentration in normality of the counter ions at which the ζ_a -potential (ζ_a) is measured, proposed by Kundu and Moulik¹] is apparent from Fig. 1, where a plot of ζ_a against $-\log \Sigma c_1$ is found to yield a straight line in each case. A and B in the above equation are constants of which A should be a constant for a particular sol, whereas B will be a constant only of the specific method of measurement for the particular sol as this quantity relates to the slope of the ζ_a - $\log \Sigma c_1$ graph which is different for different methods of measurements.

As regards coagulation of the above sols, wide deviations from Verwey and Overbeek's inverse sixth power rule have been observed. The coagulation phenomenon may now be described by the above equation which may be rewritten as

$$\Sigma c_1 = e^{(\zeta_a - A)/B} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) shows that the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte depends not only on the valency but also on the ζ_a -potential of the sol at that concentration.

The combination of equation 1 or 2 with the equation of Kundu and Moulik¹ will provide a limiting concentration value. This is obtained by extrapolating the ζ_a - $\log \Sigma c_1$

curve up to ζ , obtained from equation 1 and/or 2. Beyond this concentration, there will be no increase in the measured ζ -potential value and hence there will exist no surface conductance.

FIG. 2

[Description of graphs and points are as in Fig. 1].

The corrected ζ -potential values, the limiting concentration of the counter ions, and the values of the constants A and B are computed in Table I.

TABLE I*

Sol.	Corrected ζ -potential.	Limiting conc. (N)	A .	$2.303 B$ (mv/log N).
Copper ferrocyanide	36.1 mv	7.9×10^{-3}	40.1 mv	0.5
Nickel ferriocyanide	18.0	4.8×10^{-3}	23.6	2.4
Ceric oxide	31.5	1.9×10^{-2}	30.7	4.3

*Values obtained from electro-osmotic and/or microcataphoretic methods.

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